
Exposition of Naya in Jaina philosophy

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Serious students of Indian philosophy are well aware of the brilliant part played by Jaina Logicians in their polemics with Hindu and Buddhist logicians in ancient and medieval India. There is no doubt about it, that Jaina logic is one of the most valuable and ancient logic of India. Specially the doctrines of non-absolutism, the method of dialectical predications and the method of standpoints are the separate and peculiar dialectic development of Jaina logic. In the present paper I Want to discuss the method of standpoints in broad outline, leaving out subtle details. Because the subject is obviously very wide in scope, it cannot be treated fully in a small dissertation like this.

My treatment of the topic falls under four sections. Viz, 1 *naya* and *syadvada*, 2. *naya* and *pramana*, 2 *Naya* and *Niksepa* and 4. Definitions and kinds of *nayas*.

Nayavada and syadvada

The method of standpoints (*nayas*) and the method of dialectical predications (*Syadvada*) are the two main wings of non-absolutism (*Anekantavada*). In the words of Siddhasena Divakara, *Nayas* offers the individual Jewels, which are strung together by means of *syadvada*, into a necklace. Logically, these are two complementary processes forming a natural and inevitable development of the relativistic presupposition of the Jaina metaphysics. They form a schema which is per-eminently one of correlative methods rather than of theories of reality, although they both presuppose and explain the primordial notion that all reality is relativistic, *Nayavada* is principally an analytical method Investigating a particular standpoint of a factual situation according to the purpose and level of the equipment of experient (*jnatr*) Making a further distinction between *nayavada* and *syadvada* (*saptabhangi*) it can be said that *nayas* refer to the parts of a thing,

whereas the *saptabhangi* refers of thing as a whole, *nayas* have relation to analysis, whereas *saptabhangi* relates to synthesis. *Nayavada* is the analytical method of knowledge while *saptabhangi* or *syadvada* as the synthetical method of knowing a thing. According to H. Jacobi. It would be more correct to say that *syadvada* is a logical development the corollary of *nayavada*. Dr A.N. Upadhye observes that *syadvada* is a corollary of *nayavada* and that the latter is analytical and Primarily conceptual and the former is synthetical and verbal. In this connection Dr. Padmarajah says- “Although not quite incorrect, this distinction is apt to the somewhat misunderstood-if we are not aware of the background against which it is made. This is because the so-called 'primary conceptual method is also verbal, in as much as it not merely requires the aid of word for the express in of its various standpoints but also has as many as three., among its seven, standpoints which are exclusively designated a *saptabhangi*”. Further he says, “Similarly, in contradiction to the verbal elements of the 'conceptual' *nayavada*, the 'mainly verbal' method of *Syadvada* is so much charged with the epistemological character that we might say that its verbal side is more instrumental than intrinsic in value”. But under *Syadvada* no distinctions, such as the verbal modes of *syadvada* and non-verbal or the epistemological modes of *syadvada* can be made since all modes are both verbal and epistemological.

2. *Naya* and *Pramana*

Knowledge is attained by means of *pramana* and *naya*. Here, *pramana* is mentioned first as it is of superior excellence because it is the source or origin of *naya*. The *nayas* are the division of *pramana*. Jaina scriptures say, “Accepting knowledge derived from *pramana*, ascertaining one particular state or mode of substance is *naya*”. Secondary, the range of *pramana* comprises all attributes. Similarly, it has been said that *pramana* is a comprehensive view, whereas *naya* is a partial view. In other words, *pramana* is called complete judgement (*sakaladesa*) while *naya* is called incomplete judgment (*vikaladesa*). Through, complete judgment, it is not possible for us to describe the infinite characteristics of an object. To overcome this difficulty, we use only one word that describes one characteristic of that object and hold the remaining characteristics to be identical with it. By this method we can describe all characteristics of an object by the description of a particular aspect only. This type of proposition is called *pramana*, *saptabhangi* or complete judgment. The identity of all other aspects with a simple aspect is proved by the identity of time, quality, substratum, relation, association and word. In the case of incomplete judgment the order is reversed. Every

judgment presupposes some difference in every aspect or quality. In regard to a complete judgement, time, quality etc. establish identity among various qualities, whereas with regard to an incomplete judgement time, quality, etc. prepare the ground for difference among various qualities. This kind of judgement is called *naya-saptabhangi* also.

In this connection, a question can be raised, how the partial truth conveyed by a *naya* is as valid as the full truth conveyed by *pramana*? The Jaina logicians attempt an answer to this by employing an analogical argument, in which they compare *naya* to a part of a Sea which is *pramana*. Now in so far as a part is identical with the whole itself, there is an essential non-difference between the two; a *naya* shares the validity, at any rate in some measure, of *pramana*. But, in so far as a *naya* is different from the whole, in some sense, it cannot be identical the whole and therefore the view of the *naya* as identical with the whole must be invalid. When it becomes invalid i.e. when its partial truth is taken to be the whole truth, It is called a *Kunaya* or *Durnaya*. According to Dr. Tatia, "the contingencies of 'Naya' and 'Durnaya' arise only when a knowledge situation is sought to be expressed in or understood through inadequate logical categories and linguistic symbols, which fail to express the knowledge in its pristine comprehensiveness unless their significance is rightly analyzed."

3. Naya and Niksepa

Etymologically, the term '*Niksepa*' stands for putting together' or 'classifying; but this meaning can hardly be recognized in the developed forms of the concept of *niksepa*. It is one such technique of exposition of words as well as interpretation of the nature of reality. Now, *naya* may be distinguished from it. *Naya* is a point of view from which we make some statement about the thing, while *niksepa* is an aspect of the thing itself. If we consider the statements merely as such, its point of view is *naya*; if we consider the fact which justifies the point of view it is *niksepa*.

4. Definition of Naya and its Kinds

The Jaina doctrine of modes or stand point, corresponds to the Greek doctrine of tropes, modes and conditions. The Jaina epistemology elaborated this doctrine in order to show that several judgments or propositions may be true about the same object, but from different

points or view. Here, it is interesting to note that each fact, however trivial it may appear, can be thoroughly understood in the context of the entire reality and only in the light of its interconnection with the rest of reality, A real is possessed of an infinite number of aspects and attributes which can be thoroughly comprehended only by a person who is directly acquainted with the whole order of the reality, in one word, who is omniscient. But this does not mean that the Jaina here offers a counsel of perfection which amounts to a counsel of despair for a person like us whose resources are limited. Though the full knowledge of all the possible characteristics even of a particle of dust cannot be claimed by any one of us, the knowledge of one or the other attribute can be attained if we are dispassionate and free from bias for one angle of vision and prepared for approaching it from other standpoints. Therefore, we must recognize that there are different ways of approach or expressing the same truth, and it is this that people may refer to when they speak of approaching the same truth from different stand points, this is the way in which the Jaina non absolutism dealt with opposed with opposed doctrines of the different schools. In this connection it can be said, "It is now not merely that all theories are on an equal footing, in the sense that we have no way of arguing for one against another, and hence the idea that one standpoint is superior to another must be left out."

If we look at an object from infinite number of views, we can say that there are infinite kinds of *nayas* because the object is composed of infinite number of characteristics and one *naya* knows only one characteristic. Therefore, there is difference of opinion among the Jainas on *nayavada* on the question of the number of *nayas*. But looking at it from a specific point of view, it is maintained that *maya* is of two kinds.

(1) *Dravyarthika* (dealing with generality) and (2) *Paryayarthika* (dealing with particularity). Again, the first is called *Arthanaya* in as much as they deal with objects of knowledge, whereas the other are called *Sabdanaya*' in as much as they pertain to terms and its meanings.

Dravyarthika is the view of looking at the identity of things, while *Paryayarthika* is the view which looks at the difference of things. Man speaks of something either from the standpoint of identity or from that of difference. Statements of things from the former point of view are put under the head of *dravyarthika*, Propositions of objects from the standpoint of difference fall under the category of *paryayarthika*. Many minor classifications of things ranging between general (*dravyarthika*) and particular

(*paryayarthika*) viewpoints are also possible. But briefly speaking, there can be only two groups of statements. The view point of identity, upon which are founded the statements of generalization, is called *Dravyarthika Naya*, while the view point of difference, upon which are founded the statements of particularization is called *paryayarthika naya*. The *dravyarthikanaya* is further divided into three categories, viz., *Naigama*, *Samgraha* and *Vyavahara*. The subdivision of the *paryayarthikanaya* are four; *Rjusutra*, *Sabda*, *Sambhirudha* and *Evamabhuta*.

(1) *Naigama*: It seems to be somewhat obscure and is therefore differently interpreted by the scholars. According to Pujyapada it relates to the purpose of intention of something which is not accomplished. For instance, a person who goes equipped with an axe is asked by any one for what purpose he is going. The person replies that he goes to fetch a wooden measure (*prastha*). But at that time the wooden measure is based on the mere intention to make it. Similarly, one is engaged in fetching fuel, water, pot etc. He is asked by another person what he does? The former replies that he cooks food (*odana*). But he is not actually cooking food. He is only engaged in activity which will ultimately result in cooking food. Thus, in each of the two examples food (*odana*) and measure (*Prastha*) there is a central purpose which gives meaning to a course of conduct of some duration. The course of conduct is represented by different modes of activity at different stages. In spite of this difference the whole series and also every individual item tend towards the idea aimed at.

Again, *Naya-karnika* says that, it views an object is possessing both the general and particular properties, because no object is posed of a general property unaccompanied with some particular property nor even of a specific property unaccompanied with the general one common to its class. Consider, for instance the statement. 'I am conscious'. Here, the property of being conscious is a general quality that exists in all living beings whereas indicates the speaker a person or an individual.

According to the true relations of the teleological and interpreting idea, this *naigama* is subdivided into three viz. *vartamana*, *bhuta* and *bhavisyat* or *bhava*. *Vartamana naigama* belong to the past, yet transferred to present. When we say that today is the *parinirvana* day of Lord Mahavira, we do not mean that the Lord Mahavira is to attain or attaining nirvana on the day we actually so spoke. The event took place many centuries ago on a corresponding day of that year. Because of this correspondence an event true of the day centuries ago is also associated with all such corresponding days of

the subsequent years. In the *Bhuta naigama* instead of looking back to the past we may look forward to a remote future, instead of detecting in the concrete present the continuity of the past, we may discover in it something which is yet to be. As for example, when on perceiving would be king, we say, 'Here comes His Royal Highness'. It means that he is not yet king now, but is going to be one soon. Similarly, we may speak of every *Bhavyajiva* a good soul as *siddhajiva*, a perfect soul. For somehow in the far off future perfection will be the goal of all; for everyone is God in the germ. Such an assertion is true according to *Bhavanaigam* or future *Naigam*.

(2) *Samgraha*: This standpoint is that which comprehends several different modes under one common head through their belonging to the same class. In other words, it deals with the general characteristic of an object or the class character of a, factual situation. As for example, 'reality is one because it exists' is position of this *naya*. It does not look at the particular properties of reality but regards the general property as its subject matter though there can be no general or universal without particular, yet the enquiring from this standpoint keeps in view the generic qualities only.

This *naya* is of two kinds, *parasangraha* (ultimate class-view) and *Apara Sangraha* (inferior class-view). Every existing thing partakes of the nature of reality. Hence, we may speak of all things as one in the ultimate Reality and it is the example of *Parasangraha naya*. But the different classes of things living and non-living included in this ultimate Reality may themselves be spoken of as different classes and it is the subject matter of the *Apara-sangraha naya*.

The fallacy of this *naya* occurs when we consider the general property alone as constituting a thing. This kind of fallacious propositions gives rise to confusion of thought, because the general Qualities alone can never constitute an actual object.

(3) *Vyavahara*: This *Naya* means the popular and conventional point of view, which rests on sense-perception of the concrete present. The concrete reality of things is sufficient for our practical life. It amounts to knowing things by their call value. It takes into consideration a general object as possessing specific properties. It does not deal with generality as does the *sangraha naya*. On the other hand, it classifies the subject matter of the *sangraha* in the mode of particularity. Examination of the specific *Dravyas*. *Jiva Dravya* and *Ajiva Dravya*, both belonging to the *Dravya* Genus, would be an illustration of the *vyavahara naya*.

Fallacy of *Vyavahara Naya* lies in wrong selection of species. When the generic correlative of specific feature is entirely ignored the resultant fallacy comes to have only the semblance of this *naya*. Which select, only four primary elements as real, is the best example of this *naya*. This type of fallacy is found in the Indian philosophy.

(4) *Rjusutra*: The argument underlying this standpoint is that of immediate utility which naturally must be grounded upon the present aspect of a thing. It denies all continuity and identity. It is purely momentary. It is important to note here that it does not refer to the past or future of the thing, in this respect it is still narrower than the *vyavaharik* present. At least for *vyavaharik* view there is a tolerable duration; for the present and the conventional things are real so, far. But according to this *naya* a thing is what it is in the present mathematical moment. To speak of duration of a thing is rejected by this view as an unwarranted assumption. Thus, it enables to secure the balance between change and permanence. Accordingly, when we claim to know a thing; we mean thereby to know it only with reference to its present substantive state (*Dravya*) name (*Nama*) and form. For example, we say, 'It is very pleasant now'. This proportion predicates something which is true of the subject only at the moment of the predication.

(5) The fallacy of this *naya* occur when the permanence of things is altogether denied. Each and every object is taken to be momentary without having any kind of general features in it

(5) *Sabda*: The present stand point of synonyms refers to the function of synonymous words which, despite their differences in tense, case; gender, number and so forth convey the same meaning. In other words, it treats synonymous words as all having, the-same sense. The meaning is that the *sabdanaya* does not concern itself with but simply deals with synonymous as if they were pure equivalents of one another. For instance, *kumbha*, *kalasa*, *ghata* are all expressive of one and the same object viz. a Jar. Again, *Jiva*, *Atman*, *Prana* etc. are synonymous terms and though these differ from one another in their etymological hearings, yet they all refer to the one and the same thing conventionally.

Fallacy of *Sabadanaya* occurs when we ignore the distinguishing features of it and deal with synonymous words -as absolutely having the same meaning. The *sabdadvaitavadins* and a few other schools in Indian Philosophy. are said to have committed this fallacy.

(6) *Samabhirudha*: It is the differentiation of term's according to their roots. The difference in the roots must mean, a corresponding difference in the terms and therefore in their meanings. In other words, it distinguishes the meanings of synonymous word's purely on etymological grounds. For instance, a jar (*Kumbha*), a pitcher (*kalasa*) and a pot (*ghata*) signify different things according to their meanings. The point is that while the *sabdanaya* would treat synonyms as equivalent words, the *samabhirudha naya* would distinguish them from one another on etymological grounds. Thus, it is only a special application of *sabdha-naya*. In becoming specialized it becomes narrower and more exaggerated than the above *nayas*. The fallacy of this *naya* consists in treating, the synonymous words as having absolutely different meanings.

(7) *Evambhuta*: Etymologically, *evambhuta* means the truth of the word and its sense in its entirety. It calls for a different designation for each of the different attitudes which the same object assumes under different conditions. In other words, it recognizes an object denoted by a word only in respect of its own natural function as suggested by the derivative meaning of that word. Thus, accordingly to this principle, the radical sense in general is not the appropriate sense of a term. Even the root signification must have different gradations and aspects. Of these various aspects and gradations in the manifestations of the thing. Only one particular aspect or gradation is contemplated by the root of a term and it is this contemplated aspect or gradation which is the legitimate meaning of the terms in its current usage. The very same thing in a different attitude must be designated by a different term altogether. For instance, Purandara should be designated as such only when he is actually engaged in the act of destroying his enemies. Similarly, the designation '*sakra*' is appropriate only when he is actually manifesting his prowess. Thus, Purandara becomes as different from *sakra* as a cow is from a *Jara*.

The fallacy of this *naya* lies in making the existence of a thing absolutely dependent on the performance of the special function with reference to Which a particular name has been

awarded to it.

Thus, each of, the seven *nayas* has a greater extent or denotation than the one which follows it. *Naigama* has thus the greatest and *ebambhuta* the least extent *Naigama* deals with real and unreal. *Samgraha* deals with real only *Vyavahara* with only a part of the real. *Sabda* with only the expression of the real. *Sambiruddha* with only one particular expression. *Evamabhuta* with only that particular expression which applies to the thing in its present activity.

In this connection, it can be noted that there cannot be a thing which is devoid of its modifications of birth and decay. On the other hand, modifications cannot exist without an abiding or eternal something, a permanent, for birth decay and stability-these three constitute the characteristic of a substance or entity. These three characteristics must dwell together in harmony to make a real definition of a thing in its integral form. In this respect each *naya*, therefore, if taken independently isolated from the other, can never yield an adequate idea of an entity. Both these therefore, divorced from each other, are wrong in their standpoints. Therefore, Jaina logicians say that "a man who, holds the view of the cumulative character of truth (*Anekantavada*) never says that a particular view is right or that a particular view is wrong. Again "if all the *nayas* arrange themselves in a proper way and supplement to each other, then alone they are worthy, of being termed as the whole truth or the right view in its entirety. But in this case they merge their individuality in the collective whole". Therefore, the right approach should be to accept the • relating validity of knowledge. In order to give a logical shape to this view the Jainas have formulated; "a theory of relative standpoint" and "they, are of opinion that there can never be an absolute claim about the truth of any expression."

At last, we can say in the words of G.H. Rao that "each philosophy approaching reality form a particular and a partial standpoint, looks upon the one they adopt as the only true standpoint. Jainas reject the idea of the absolute which is playing havoc in the field of philosophy by creating absolute monism, absolute pluralism, and absolute nihilism. By thus rejecting the absolute and one-sided, they claim to save philosophy from the chaos of conflicting opinions. Without partiality to any one they promise to give us a theory of relativity which harmonizes all standpoints."

Notes and References

1. Siddhasena Divakar, SanmatitarkahPrakarana, Gatha- 22-25.
2. Padmarajiah, Y.J. *Jaina Theories of Reality and Knowledge*, p. 301
3. Jacob, H- Studies in Jainism, p. 17, 52
4. Upadhye, A.N. (ed) *Pravacanasara*, Introduction-LXXXV
5. Padmarajiah, Y.J. *Jaina Theories of Reality and Knowledge*, p. 304
6. Ibid.,. P. 305
7. Pujiyapada, *Sarvarthasiddhi, Sutra - 6*
8. *Satkhandagama*, p. 163. Vidyananda, Tattvarthasloka Varttika 1-6.
9. Suri, Vadideva : *Syadvada-ratnakara* vol. IV., p. 44.
10. Vidyananda: *Astahasri*, p. 209
11. do *Tattvarthaslokavarttika*, 1-6
12. Samantabhadra : *Aptamimamsa, Gatha - 108*; Vidyananda : *Astahasri*, p. 290
13. Tatia, N.: *Acarya Bhiksu Commemoration Vol. Sec. III*, P. 103
14. *Jayadhavala*, p. 283; *Sthananga - 209*

There are four distinct phases of the develop meet of the doctrine in the exegetical and logical literature of the *Jnanas*, Viz.

Niksenas as doctrine of verbal usage,

Nikespa as a doctrine of aspects of reality

Nama-niksepa as entailing a doctrine of import of words and

Niksepa as a critique of absolutism.

Dr. Tatia, *Acarya Bhiksu commemoration volume*, Sect. III, p. 71

15. Raju, P.T. *The philosophical Traditions of India*, p. 97
16. Hemachandra : *Anya-yoga-vyavaccheda dvatrimasika*, SU-5, *Akalanka Laghistraya - Tika-62*
17. There are mainly three traditions which are based on the number of *nayas* occurring in the classification adopted by each of them within the framework of reality which is conceived to be fundamentally *dravya paryayarthika*. The first one adopts a classification of seven, our treatment of the subject has been based on this classification. The second tradition drops *nama* which is the first among the seven *nayas* recognised by the first tradition. The third tradition reduces the number from seven to five by sub-summing *samabhirudha* and *evambhuta*, the last two standpoints under *sabda*, and thus treating them as two subdivisions of the *sabdanaya*.

Dr. Padmrajiah, *Jaina Theories of Reality and knowledge*, p. 325

18. Siddhasena Diakara : *Sanmatitarka Prakarana - 1.3*.
19. Suri, Vadideva : *Pramana-naya tattvaloka*, Vol. VII, P.6
20. Ibid., p. 27

21. Vinaya Viaya : *Nayakarnika - Sutra-5*. Akalanka. *Tattvartha-raja vartika* 1/33.
Suri, Vadideva : *Syadvada-ratnakara*, Vol.V. P.1052
Prabhacandra *Nayakumudacandra*, p. 84 Vidyananda : *Tattavarthaslokavarttika*, p. 249.
Samantabhadra : *Laghiyastraya*, p. 39, 68
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24. Vinayavijaya; *Naya Karnika, Sutra 8*; Suri, Vadideva : *Pramana naya tattvaioka* - vol. V11-23-4
- 25 . I b i d .
Prabhacandra : *Nyayakumudacandra*, p. 636,792
Samantabhadra : *Laghiyastraya, Karika* 43,71
26. Vinayavijaya : *Naya Karnika, Sutra 14* Akalanka : *Tattvarthavaratika* - 1 /33
Vidyananda : *Tattvarthaslokavartika* p. 272, 273.
27. Siddhasena Divakara: *Nayavavatara* (Ed. P.L. Vaidya), p.82.
28. Vinayavijaya : *Naya Karnika sutra 15*
Prabhacandra : *Nayakumudacandra* vol. U. p. 638
29. Suri, Vadideva, *Pramananayatattvaloka*, vol. VII. 36
30. I b i d . p . 40
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31. Sidasena Divakara : *Sanmatitarka, Gatha* 1; 12,13
Pujoyapada: *Sarvartha Siddhi, Sutra* 30
32. Siddhasena Divakara : *Sanmatitarka, Gatha* 1/25,28
33. Pandey, R.C. : *A Panorama of Indian Philosophy*, p. 44
34. Rao, G.H. : The half yearly Journal of the Mysore University (1942) pp. 79-80.